

1 Hydraulic performance analysis for homogeneous mound
2 breakwaters: application of dimensional analysis and a new
3 experimental technique

4 Pilar Díaz-Carrasco¹

5 ¹*Department of Transportation, ETSI Caminos, Universitat Politècnica de València, 46022, Valencia, Spain;*
6 *pdiacar@upv.es*

7 **Abstract**

8 The main objective of this study is to apply the methodology proposed by ?, based on the
9 dimensional analysis and a new experimental technique, to estimate and study the wave energy
10 transformation on homogeneous mound breakwaters. The dimensional analysis includes the main
11 variables of wave train, porous media and slope geometry that influence the hydraulic perfor-
12 mance on mound breakwaters. For that, laboratory tests were performed in a wave flume for a
13 homogeneous and permeable mound breakwater. A new experimental technique derived from the
14 methodology of ? is also applied for designing wave conditions in laboratory based on the interplay
15 that the relative water depth, h/L , and the wave steepness, H/L , has on the hydraulic performance
16 of the structure, called the sample space. An analysis was conducted to study the influence that
17 each dimensionless variable has on wave energy transformation. The experimental results shows
18 that there is a relationship between the reflected, K_R^2 , transmitted, K_T^2 , and dissipated energy, D^* ,
19 and the product of the relative water depth, h/L , and the incident wave steepness, H_I/L . The se-
20 lection of wave conditions from the new experimental technique of sample space allows quantifying
21 regions of wave energy transformation and wave breaker types on the breakwater and it seems to
22 be a useful technique for designing laboratory conditions.

23 *Keywords:* Mound breakwaters, Laboratory technique, Wave energy transformation,
24 Wave-breaking, Porous media, Relative water depth, Wave steepness

Symbol	Definition
B_b	Crown width
B_{eq}	Characteristic width (?)
B^*	Base width
D^*	Bulk dissipation energy
$D_{n50,a}$	Armour diameter
$D_{n50,p}$	Core diameter
F_{MT}	Height of the breakwater

Symbol	Definition
F_c	Free-board
g	Gravity acceleration
h	Water depth
H	Wave height
H_I	Incident wave height
K_R	Wave reflection coefficient
K_T	Wave transmission coefficient
L	Wavelength obtained by the wave period T and linear dispersion
n_p	Core porosity
$R_{e,Da}$	Armor Reynolds number
$R_{e,p}$	Core Reynolds number
T	Wave period
U	$\approx n_p H/T$ Characteristic seepage velocity
α	Seaward slope angle
β	Landward slope angle
χ	Similarity parameter defined by ?
ν	Kinematic water viscosity
ρ_s	Rock/Cube unit density
ξ	$= \tan(\alpha)/\sqrt{(H/L)}$ Iribarren number

25 1. Introduction

26 Rubble mound breakwater is the most frequent breakwater typology in the world due to its
27 ability to dissipate the wave energy, its relatively simple design and the possibility to be constructed
28 using pieces of different types and sizes. Within this typology, use of homogeneous and permeable
29 mound breakwaters without multi-layer cross sections has seen a pronounced expansion in coastal
30 engineering. Most of these structures are built to protect navigation channels and harbours, but
31 they are also considered for using in beach stabilisation and shore protection (??). In general, the
32 latter applications are possible thanks to the advantages offered by this mound typology compared
33 to others, such as: (1) its high porosity makes it more stable than a rubble mound breakwater
34 with main armour layer, (2) it dissipates energy effectively and, (3) its design simplicity and
35 low environment impact are significant factors in keeping down constructions costs and being an
36 optimum structure and a natural-based solution in many situations (??).

37 The design project, construction and maintenance of mound breakwaters must be verified
38 to provide safety and service in coastal areas during its useful life. The performance of these
39 coastal structures depends on the kinematic and dynamic regimes and its quantification should

40 consider the three laws of (1) energy conservation, used to estimate the energy transformation in
41 wave-structure interaction; (2) mass conservation, applicable to estimate run-up, run-down and
42 overtopping; and (3) momentum conservation, used to calculate the forces and momentums on the
43 pieces that form the structure (stability analysis). In order to design stability and overtopping
44 formulas for these coastal structures, their hydraulic performance should first be analysed, which
45 includes the phenomena of wave progression and energy transformation (reflected, K_R^2 , transmitted,
46 K_T^2 , dissipated energy, D^*) on the slope.

47 Most of the formulas used for quantifying the hydraulic performance on mound breakwaters
48 are based on the seminal work of ?, who proposed using Iribarren number, ξ , (?) as the dynamic
49 similarity parameter to analyse wave energy transformation on breakwaters and to identify wave
50 breaker types over the slope. Since then, most of the design formulas are combinations of Iribarren
51 number with both dimensionless and dimension variables selected on empirical grounds rather than
52 on dimensional analysis. ???? demonstrated that there is a high scatter of the wave energy for-
53 mulas, breaker types, overtopping and stability formulas, as the Iribarren number increases. These
54 current experimental formulas are derived from an extensive experimental database and fitted
55 by calibrating coefficients and including/mixing variables without prior analysis of the parameters
56 that influence the design variable. In addition, the formulas obtained are derived from experiments
57 tested with very specific test conditions, experimental devices and techniques. The consequences
58 of these analyses and methods result in a high epistemic uncertainty of the results and thus of the
59 developed formulas. This uncertainty seems unacceptable not only because of the knowledge and
60 means available, but also because of the future challenges resulting from sea level rise that will
61 require greater precision and optimisation (economically and environmentally) in design.

62 Consequently, the main objective of this study is to apply a specific methodology developed
63 in recent years by ? in order to estimates and study the energy transformation of incident waves
64 that interact with a homogeneous mound breakwater. The methodology is based on dimensional
65 analysis which includes the main variables of wave train, porous media and slope geometry that
66 influence the hydraulic performance of slope breakwaters. A new experimental technique derived
67 from the methodology of ? is also applied for designing laboratory tests based on the interplay that
68 the relative water depth, h/L , and the wave steepness, H/L , has on the hydraulic performance of
69 the structure. This study involves physical laboratory experimentation in a 2D wave flume of a
70 non-overtoppable, homogeneous and permeable mound breakwater. The structure of the paper is
71 organised as follows: Section 2 gathers a background of the dimensional analysis and main results of
72 ?. Section 3 outlines the physical tests, experimental technique and processing methods performed
73 in IISTA-University of Granada. Section 4 presents the results of wave energy transformation and
74 breaker types according to the variables involved in the dimensional analysis. The discussion of the
75 experimental technique and results is gathered in Section 5. Conclusions are presented in Section
76 6. Finally, Appendix A details the application of the new experimental technique for selecting

77 wave conditions in laboratory.

78 2. Background of wave-structure interaction analysis

79 ? studied the wave energy transformation for an impermeable slope breakwater and a permeable slope breakwater with main armour layer on the basis of numerical and experimental tests, 80 respectively. From these experiments, rough slope and smooth slope, ? included the main geometrical and wave parameters involved in both breakwater typologies and developed a dimensional 81 analysis (described in detail in their study) which states that the wave energy reflected (K_R^2), 82 transmitted (K_T^2) and dissipated (D^*) are derived quantities of: 83 84

$$[K_R^2, K_T^2, D^*] = f(\Pi_1, \Pi_2, \Pi_3) \quad (1)$$

85 where $\Pi_1 = (h/L, H_I/L)$ represents the incident wave train that includes the relative water depth, 86 h/L , and the wave steepness at the toe of the slope, H_I/L . $\Pi_2 = (B^*/L, D_{n50,p}/L, R_{e,p})$ gathers 87 the influence of the porous media with: the relative base width, B^*/L , that indicates the tendency 88 to reach the saturation regime of the structure (?); the relative core diameter, $D_{n50,p}/L$, that 89 governs the flow dissipation inside the porous media and quantifies the scale effects (?); and the 90 grain Reynolds number, $R_{e,p} = D_{n50,p}U/\nu$ (???), being $U \approx n_p H/T$ the characteristic seepage 91 velocity in the porous media. $\Pi_3 = (D_{n50,a}/L, R_{e,Da})$, includes the influence of the main armour 92 layer with: the relative main armour diameter, $D_{n50,a}/L$, that governs the turbulence flow on 93 the slope due to the wave-breaking and interaction with the armour layer (?); and the armour 94 Reynolds number, $R_{e,Da} \approx \sqrt{gH_I}D_{n50,a}/\nu$ (?). The slope angle, α , is not included in Eq. 1 since 95 it is already a dimensionless parameter that characterises the structure and orders the results.

96 From the dimensional analysis and the experimental results, ? pointed out the following conclusions, 97

- 98 1. The regions of wave energy transformation and their related breaker types are the following:
 - 99 (i) dissipated region with spilling and weak plunging breakers; (ii) reflected region with
 - 100 surging breakers; and (iii) transition region, with strong plunging, strong bore and weak bore
 - 101 breakers. ?'s study includes the variants of breaker types referred to weak/strong plunging
 - 102 (?) and weak/strong bore (?).
- 103 2. There is a relationship between the product $(h/L)(H_I/L)$ and the reflected, transmitted and
- 104 dissipated energy on slope breakwaters. This product is defined as the similarity parameter
- 105 $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$, which delimits the wave energy transformation regions (reflected,
- 106 dissipated and transition regions) and the wave trains with the same breaker type (?).
- 107 3. The sample space defined by $[\log(h/L)$ vertical-axis, $\log(H/L)$ horizontal-axis] provides a
- 108 functional relationship between water depth, h , wave height, H , and wave period, T . This
- 109 functional relationship would allow designing experimental conditions in laboratory in order

110 to characterize the regions of wave energy transformation and wave breaker types on mound
 111 breakwaters.

112 The main results of ? suggest applying this analysis methodology to more laboratory tests in
 113 order to verify the correct study of wave-structure interaction.

114 3. Experimental setup

115 3.1. Physical tests

116 Experimental tests were performed in the wave flume of the Andalusian Inter-University Insti-
 117 tute for Earth System Research (IISTA) at the University of Granada (Fig. 1a). Fig. 1b shows a
 118 diagram of the physical model tested, namely, a homogeneous and permeable mound breakwater
 119 with a constant granular diameter, $D_{n50,p} = 30$ mm. Two different widths of the top, B_b , and
 120 two seaward slope angles, α , were tested. The water depth in the wave generation zone and in the
 121 flume was kept constant and equal to $h = 0.4$ m.

Figure 1: (a) Diagram of the wave flume and location of wave gauges (dimensions in meters), (b) physical model of the homogeneous and permeable mound breakwater tested (HP-MB).

122 Table 2 summarises the geometrical configuration of the three physical models tested, identified
 123 hereinafter as: HP-MB-1, for $B_b = 0.24$ m, slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$; HP-MB-2, for $B_b = 0.24$ m, slope
 124 $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$; and HP-MB-3, for $B_b = 0.10$ m, slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$. All the models have a constant
 125 free-board, $F_c = 0.15$ m and a breakwater height, $F_{MT} = 0.55$ m. The characteristic of the
 126 permeable and homogeneous rocks were: diameter $D_{n50,p} = 30$ mm, density $\rho_s = 2.64$ tn/m³, and
 127 porosity $n_p = 0.462$ according to ?.

128 3.2. New experimental technique: the sample space

129 The application of new experimental technique proposed by ?, called the sample space $[\log(h/L),$
 130 $\log(H/L)]$, seeks to (i) optimize the number of experiments, (ii) verify the design criteria between

Configuration	B_b (m)	$\tan(\alpha)$	$\tan(\beta)$	B^* (m)
HP-MB-1	0.24	1/2	1/1.5	2.165
HP-MB-2	0.24	1/1.5	1/1.5	1.890
HP-MB-3	0.10	1/2	1/1.5	2.025

Table 2: Geometric parameters of the physical models tested. B_b is the crown width of the breakwater; B^* is the base width of the breakwater; and α and β are the seaward and landward slopes of the breakwater, respectively.

131 model-prototype, and (iii) quantify the regions of wave energy transformation and wave breaker
132 types. Fig. 2 shows the flow-chart of the sample space to select the wave conditions in laboratory
133 according to experimental requirements. The wave conditions of wave height, H , and wave period,
134 T (or wavelength, L by dispersion equation $f(h, T)$), for a given water depth, h , can be selected
135 as follow:

- 136 • *Step 1:* According to the experimental requirements, such as experimental tests under non-
137 overtopping (E1), non-damage (E2) and non-breaking wave conditions (E3), the wave height
138 could be limited to a maximum value, H_{max} and $H/h < 0.78$. The wave generation regime
139 (E3) should be also considered as well as the limitations of the laboratory's paddle generation
140 (E5).
- 141 • *Step 2:* Depending on the breakwater typology and considering values of previous studies
142 and constructed maritime works of this typology, it is possible to select wave conditions of
143 H and T that achieve the maximum reflected (R) and dissipated (D) wave energy. Points R
144 and D close the formed parallelepiped in which h/L and H/L conditions are selected.
- 145 • *Step 3:* Selecting h/L and H/L conditions to cover the transitions of wave breaker types,
146 such as weak/strong bore and weak/strong plunging.

147 This section summarises the wave conditions obtained from the application of the flow-chart of
148 Fig. 2 to the mound breakwaters and experiments of this study. Appendix A describes in detail
149 the direct application of the sample space for the laboratory tests of this study.

150 The experimental tests were performed with the following requirements:

- 151 1. Wave-breaking was only caused by wave-breakwater interaction and the experiments were
152 also under non-overtopping and non-damage conditions.
- 153 2. The AwaSys software package was used to generate waves with the simultaneously active
154 absorption of reflected waves. The IISTA paddle generation system was limited by: $H >$
155 0.02 m and $T > 1$ s.
- 156 3. Regular waves in Stoke I regime were simulated and defined by a wave height, H , and a wave
157 period, T . Each test was repeated three times with 100 of waves per test.

158 Regular wave conditions of H and T (target conditions) were selected by complying with the
159 functional relationship of the sample space $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ to cover the regions of wave

Figure 2: Flow-chart of the new experimental technique proposed by ?, called sample space, to select the wave conditions in laboratory according to the experimental requirements.

160 energy transformation and breaker types. Note that throughout this study when the wave height
161 is identified by H or H_I it refers to the conditions of target and incident wave height (obtained
162 by separation of the incident and reflected wave trains), respectively. Table 3 gathers the wave
163 conditions for the three physical models tested. For further information on the application of this
164 experimental technique see Appendix A.

Wave parameter	Range
T (s)	[1.02 – 3.64]
H (m)	[0.0205 – 0.121]
h/L	[0.06 – 0.28]
H/L	[0.005 – 0.026]

Table 3: Minimum and maximum values of waves conditions tested in laboratory (H, T) following the sample space [$\log(h/L), \log(H_I/L)$] described in Appendix A.

165 3.3. Wave measurements and data processing

166 The experimental incident and reflected wave trains were separated using the method suggested
167 by ?, which gives the magnitude and phase of the reflected wave train. The reflected and trans-
168 mitted wave energy, E_R, E_T , and their respective reflection (K_R^2 and phase ϕ_R) and transmission
169 coefficients (K_T^2) were obtained by applying power spectral analysis. K_R^2 and ϕ_R were calculated
170 with the data measured by gauges G1, G2 and G3 (see Fig. 1a). The transmission coefficient
171 (K_T^2) was computed with the data measured with gauge G5. Gauge G4, located at the toe of
172 the structure ($x = 0$), provided the total wave height at the toe of the breakwater (due to the

173 interaction of the incident and reflected wave trains). The total bulk dissipation per unit of wave
 174 incident energy, D^* , is determined by solving the wave energy conservation equation

$$K_R^2 + K_T^2 + D^* = 1 \quad (2)$$

175 The statistical parameters of incident wave height, H_I , wave period, T , and wavelength, L ,
 176 were obtained from the temporal analysis of the time series. For each regular test, wave breakers
 177 on breakwater slope were identified by photographs and test recording; thus, surging, weak/strong
 178 bore and weak/strong plunging breakers were identified.

179 4. Analysis of wave-structure interaction results

180 This section analyses the results of wave energy transformation [K_R^2 , K_T^2 , D^*] for the ho-
 181 mogeneous and permeable mound breakwaters tested by the following steps: first, the hydraulic
 182 performance of the permeable breakwater (rough slope) is compared with the numerical results
 183 obtained in the IH-2VOF model (?) of an impermeable breakwater (smooth slope) with the same
 184 slope and water depth condition (see Appendix B for further details of the numerical tests); then,
 185 the influence on wave energy transformation of the dimensionless parameters representing the
 186 incident wave train, the porous media, and the slope angle, is analysed.

187 4.1. Hydraulic performance of a permeable slope versus an impermeable slope

188 Fig. 3a and Fig. 3b show the sample spaces [$\log(h/L)$, $\log(H_I/L)$] for the impermeable break-
 189 water modelled numerically in IH-2VOF by ? and the homogeneous and permeable HP-MB-1
 190 model tested in this study, respectively. For both breakwaters the water depth was constant, h
 191 = 0.4 m, and the slope angle $\cot(\alpha) = 2$. Wave breaker types are identified by colour-bands for
 192 the impermeable slope and by colours for the permeable HP-MB-1 slope. The isolines of constant
 193 values of $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$ are also marked. It is observed that in both sample spaces the density
 194 of the results is similar in the range $0.001 \leq \chi \leq 0.0065$. This region corresponds to wave heights
 195 and wave periods normally tested both in laboratory and numerically. For the permeable slope,
 196 whose wave conditions (H and T) comes from the experimental technique detailed in Appendix
 197 A, this range $0.001 \leq \chi \leq 0.0065$ encompasses the zones selected to cover the transitions of wave
 198 breaker types (weak/strong bore and weak/strong plunging). Comparing both sample spaces it
 199 is observed that, for the same slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and $h = 0.4$ m, the breaker types for the homo-
 200 geneous and permeable HP-MB-1 breakwater are shifted to lower values of χ with respect to the
 201 impermeable one. For instance, the same breaker type, strong plunging, occurs with lower values
 202 of wave steepness H_I/L and relative depth h/L in the permeable slope case. The presence of a
 203 porous media, in particular the flow within it, changes and determines the phase lag between the
 204 incident and reflected wave trains and this impacts on the wave breaker type. For the same relative

205 water depth and wave steepness, wave-breaking will tend to be more dissipative breaker type on a
 206 permeable slope than on an impermeable slope.

Figure 3: Sample spaces $[\log(h/L), \log(H_I/L)]$ for (a) an impermeable slope breakwater with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ modelled by χ , and (b) the homogeneous and permeable slope HP-MB-1 tested in laboratory with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$. Black line represents the isolines with constant values χ . Colours are used to identify the breaker types.

207 Fig. 4 represents the results of wave energy transformation coefficients against the similarity
 208 parameter $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$, for the same data represented in Fig. 3: (circles) homogeneous and
 209 permeable HP-MB-1 model with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$, (triangles) impermeable slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ of
 210 χ . Despite having the same slope angle, the results for the permeable slope are shifted to lower
 211 values of χ . For the same value of χ , the permeable breakwater reflects much less energy with
 212 more dissipated breaker types (Fig. 3) than the impermeable structure. Fig. 4 also shows that for
 213 small variations in χ , with $\chi > 10^{-3}$, different wave breaker types are observed in laboratory, from
 214 weak bore to weak plunging with increasing χ , and large variations in K_R^2 , D^* and K_T^2 occur. A
 215 remarkable feature in the experimental results is the presence of a data set for the surging and weak
 216 bore breaker types, leading to different K_R^2 values for the same χ value depending on the breaker
 217 type (e.g. $\chi = 0.001$). Coincidentally, the highest K_T^2 values occur in this data set (hereinafter
 218 referred to as singularity). In the impermeable slope, for the same value of χ , for example $\chi = 0.002$,
 219 it is observed some dispersion in K_R^2 results but the wave breaker types are ordered according to
 220 χ values as it is shown in Fig. 3a. Specifically, in the interval $0.002 \leq \chi \leq 0.0065$, it is observed
 221 weak bore, strong bore and strong plunging breaker types, which generate a dispersion in wave
 222 energy transformation (χ).

223 The comparison of permeable results to those of the impermeable breakwater with the same
 224 slope angle highlighted significant changes in the performance of the permeable breakwater. The
 225 different behaviour of the permeable breakwater compared with the impermeable one is due to the
 226 role that the porous media and its interaction with the incident wave train (h/L , H_I/L) has in
 227 the hydraulic performance of the homogeneous and permeable structure. As pointed out in χ , for

Figure 4: Wave energy transformation against the product of the wave steepness and the relative water depth, $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$: (a) reflected energy coefficient K_R^2 , (b) bulk wave dissipation D^* , and (c) transmitted energy coefficient K_T^2 . Circles-symbols are the experimental results of the homogeneous and permeable slope HP-MB-1 tested with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and $B^* = 2.165$ m, and triangle-symbols are the numerical results of the impermeable slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ modelled by ?. The breaker types of the experimental results are identified by colours.

228 a homogeneous and permeable breakwater the wave energy transformation (K_R^2 , K_T^2 and D^*) and
 229 wave breaker types also depend on the relative width, B^*/L , the relative core diameter, $D_{n50,p}/L$,
 230 and the grain Reynolds number, R_{ep} .

231 4.2. Influence of dimensionless parameters on hydraulic performance

232 This section analyses the influence of the dimensionless parameters presented in Eq. 1 for
 233 a homogeneous and permeable breakwater (Π_1 , Π_2 in Eq. 1), which are not constant in the
 234 experimental tests, and the slope angle, α . In the following the experimental results of dissipation,
 235 D^* , are not represented since its values follow a opposite trend to the reflection coefficient (K_R^2),
 236 because of the low values of transmission coefficients ($K_T^2 < 0.06$).

237 4.2.1. Incident wave train

238 Fig. 5 represents the influence of the incident wave train, h/L and H_I/L , on the experimental
 239 results for the homogeneous and permeable HP-MB-1 model with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and base width
 240 $B^* = 2.165$ m. Figs. 5-a.1 and 5-b.1 locate the ranges of values of h/L and H_I/L in the sample
 241 space and its relation with the regions of wave energy transformation and breaker types. For the
 242 lower values of relative water depth, $h/L \leq 0.07$, the maximum reflection of the structure occurs
 243 (Fig. 5-a.2) and surging/weak bore breaker types are observed (see Figs. 3b and 4). As h/L
 244 increases and for wave steepness $H_I/L > 0.01$ (Fig 5b), the wave breaker types progress from weak
 245 bore to weak plunging, and the reflection of the breakwater decreases (see Figs. 5-a.2 and 5-b.2,

246 respectively). For wave energy transmitted, small changes in h/L do not result in large changes in
 247 K_T^2 .

Figure 5: Analysis of the incident wave train characterised by: (a) the relative water depth, h/L , and (b) the wave steepness, H_I/L . Figs (a.1) and (b.1) are the sample spaces coloured by ranges of h/L and H_I/L , respectively. Figs. (a.2, a.3) and Figs. (b.2, b.3) represent the reflected energy coefficient, K_R^2 , and transmitted energy coefficient, K_T^2 , against χ coloured by ranges of h/L and H_I/L , respectively. The experimental results are for the homogeneous and permeable HP-MB-1 model with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and base width $B^* = 2.165$ m.

248 For each range of wave steepness H_I/L defined $-H_I/L \leq 0.01$, $0.01 < H_I/L \leq 0.02$, $0.02 <$
 249 H_I/L – Fig. 5-b.2 shows that the reflection coefficient is larger ($K_R^2 > 0.3$) or smaller ($K_R^2 < 0.1$)
 250 depending on whether h/L value is high or low, respectively (Fig. 5-a.2). As H_I/L increases, K_T^2
 251 decreases (Fig. 5-b.3) and breaker types progress from surging to weak plunging (Figs. 3b and 4).
 252 For the experimental data with $H_I/L \leq 0.01$, the transmitted coefficient takes the highest values
 253 (maximum $K_T^2 = 0.057$) and the breaker types observed are surging and weak bore. These values
 254 of $H_I/L \leq 0.01$ are in the singularity mentioned in Fig. 4.

255 Fig. 5 shows that as χ increase, K_R^2 and K_T^2 decrease except at the singularity mentioned
 256 above with values of $H_I/L \leq 0.01$. It seems that the results of wave reflection and transmission
 257 depend more on the relative water depth and on the wave steepness, respectively: K_R^2 decreases
 258 as h/L increases and K_T^2 decreases as H_I/L increases. Wave breaker types are ordered according
 259 to increasing values of χ , from surging to weak plunging. The breaker type conditions the amount
 260 of reflected, dissipated and transmitted energy. For a constant water depth, h , as the wave period
 261 decreases and wave height increases, the incident wave train becomes more unstable and tend to
 262 dissipate more energy when it interacts with the structure. The more energy dissipated (lower
 263 K_R^2), the lower flow through the porous media and therefore lower values of K_T^2 .

264 4.2.2. Geometric configuration of the porous media

265 Fig. 6 represents the sample space and the experimental values of K_R^2 and K_T^2 against χ ,
 266 coloured by ranges of B^*/L , for the two physical models tested with different size of porous media:
 267 (circles) HP-MB-1 model with top width $B_b = 0.24$ m and base width $B^* = 2.165$ m, (squares)
 268 HP-MB-3 model with top width $B_b = 0.10$ m and base width $B^* = 2.025$ m. For both models,
 269 the slope angle is $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and the diameter of the porous media is $D_{n50,p} = 30$ mm. Fig.
 270 6a locates the ranges of values of B^*/L in the sample space and its relation with the regions of
 271 wave energy transformation and breaker types. Fig. 6 shows that the range of values of B^*/L are
 272 grouped in the same intervals of χ for both models with different porous media area. The reflected
 273 energy of the breakwater, K_R^2 , increases (D^* decreases) as B^*/L decreases (Fig 6b). For large
 274 relative width, $B^*/L > 3/4$ or $B_{eq}/L > 0.25$ (being B_{eq} a characteristic width of the porous media
 275 (?)), the reflection coefficient achieves a minimum and constant value. In this region and for the
 276 results with $H_I/L > 0.01$ (Fig. 5), the wave energy dissipated, D^* , takes the highest values and
 277 the breaker types observed are strong/weak plunging (Fig. 4). The transmitted energy, K_T^2 , takes
 278 maximum and minimum values with the lowest and highest range of B^*/L , respectively (Fig. 6c).
 279 The trend is that K_T^2 decreases as B^*/L increases although it is not as evident as in K_R^2 results. In
 280 intermediate B^*/L ranges, K_T^2 results depends more on the wave steepness and the wave breaker
 281 type.

Figure 6: Analysis of the porous media characterised by the relative base width B^*/L , whose ranges are identified by colours: (a) sample spaces with the isolines of χ constant marked (black-lines); (b) and (c) the reflected energy coefficient, K_R^2 , and transmitted energy coefficient, K_T^2 , against χ , respectively. The experimental results are for the homogeneous and permeable models: (circles-symbols) HP-MB-1 model slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and base width $B_b = 0.24$ m, (squares-symbols) HP-MB-3 model slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and base width $B_b = 0.10$ m.

282 Fig. 6 shows that the results of K_R^2 and K_T^2 for range of B^*/L have the same trend as for h/L
 283 ranges (Fig. 5-a.2). The relative width of the breakwater, B^*/L , marks the saturation regime of
 284 the structure in laboratory, that is, when the breakwater cannot reflect and transmit (throw the

285 porous media) more energy, and it reaches a constant minimum value of K_R^2 . For the results with
 286 $H_I/L > 0.01$, the saturation regime is achieved at $\chi \approx 0.002$ for range of $B^*/L > 1$, with minimum
 287 values of K_R^2 and K_T^2 . In the singularity mentioned with $H_I/L \leq 0.01$, there are minimum values
 288 of K_R^2 with $3/4 < B^*/L < 1$ but these values do not correspond to a saturation regime since K_T^2
 289 takes high values; the origin of this singularity will be explained below.

290 4.2.3. Seaward slope angle

291 Fig. 7 shows the influence of the seaward slope angle, α , in the hydraulic performance of the
 292 structure. Wave breaker types are identified by colours. The experimental results show that K_R^2
 293 results are ordered by the slope angle. In fact, there is a slight displacement along the x-axis to
 294 higher values of χ for the experimental data with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$. This displacement is also
 295 reflected in the sample space shown in Fig. 7a. For the same value of χ and breaker type, e.g.
 296 $\chi = 0.002$ and weak bore breaker, the slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$ tends to reflect more energy (dissipate
 297 less) than the slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ (Fig. 7b). In this case, the transmitted energy for $\chi = 0.002$ and
 298 weak bore breaker is practically the same for both slope angles (Fig. 7c). Except for the singularity
 299 data mentioned, Fig. 7 also shows that wave breaker types are ordered by values of χ , from weak
 300 bore to weak plunging as χ increases, for each slope angle tested.

Figure 7: Analysis of the slope angle α : (a) sample spaces with the isolines of χ constant marked (black-lines); (b) and (c) the reflected energy coefficient, K_R^2 , and transmitted energy coefficient, K_T^2 , against χ , respectively. The experimental results are for the homogeneous and permeable models: (circles) HP-MB-1 model slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$, (triangles) HP-MB-2 model slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$. Wave breaker types are identified by colours.

301 Although the differences between the two slopes angles are not significant because the tested
 302 slopes are very close to each other, Fig. 7 shows that as the slope angle increases, the breakwater
 303 tends to reflect more energy and dissipate less. The maximum reflection would occur with a
 304 completely vertical wall. In the case of transmitted energy by flow inside the porous media, both
 305 slopes have practically the same values of K_T^2 for each value of χ and wave breaker type. Note

306 that for $\chi > 0.002$ corresponding also to $B^*/L > 1$ (Fig. 6), both slope angles reflect the same
 307 energy since both slopes achieve the saturation regime in laboratory.

308 4.2.4. Flow regimes inside the porous media

Figure 8: Analysis of flow regimes inside the porous media. Colours delimit the flow regimes according to intervals of grain Reynolds number, $R_{e,p}$, established by ? : (a) sample spaces with the isolines of χ constant marked (black-lines); (b) and (c) the reflected energy coefficient, K_R^2 , and transmitted energy coefficient, K_T^2 , against χ , respectively. The experimental results are for the three homogeneous and permeable models tested: (circles) HP-MB-1, (triangles) HP-MB-2, (squares) HP-MB-3.

309 Flow regimes inside the porous media for the three permeable and homogeneous tested break-
 310 waters are gathered in Fig. 8. The flow regimes limits are established according to ? by interval
 311 of grain Reynolds number, $R_{e,p} = UD_{n50,p}/\nu$. Fig. 8a locates the ranges of values of $R_{e,p}$ in
 312 the sample space and its relation with the regions of wave energy transformation and breaker
 313 types. Results show that laminar ($R_{e,p} < 150$), transition ($150 < R_{e,p} < 300$), and turbulent
 314 ($R_{e,p} > 300$) flow regimes are present inside the porous media. It is observed that in the laminar
 315 regime, wave steepness is $H_I/L < 0.01$ (Fig. 5b) and only surging breaker types are observed (Fig.
 316 4). In this regime, the K_R^2 decreases (dissipation increases) with increasing χ (Fig. 8b), but the
 317 K_T^2 results are maximum in this interval (Fig. 8c). For the transition regime, the values of K_R^2
 318 are high or low (conversely D^*) for the same χ value, K_T^2 decreases with increasing χ , and surg-
 319 ing/weak bore breakers types are observed (Fig. 4) with values of wave steepness, $H_I/L < 0.01$
 320 and $0.01 < H_I/L < 0.02$ (Fig. 5b).

321 Fig. 8 shows that the singularity data mentioned above are in laminar and transition regimes,
 322 with high values of K_T^2 , surging and weak bore breakers observed, and maximum and minimum
 323 K_R^2 values for the same value of χ . In the turbulent regime, K_R^2 and K_T^2 decrease with increasing χ ,
 324 and the breaker types observed progress from weak bore to weak plunging with increasing χ (Fig.
 325 5b). Hence, it seems that in the laminar and transition flow regimes the hydraulic performance of

326 the structure with χ changes with respect to the hydraulic performance in the turbulent regime.

327 The flow regime inside the porous media depends also on the relative diameter of the porous
328 media, D_{n50}/L (?). In this experimental tests, D_{n50} is constant for the three physical models.
329 Although the effect of D_{n50}/L cannot be analysed in this study, it seems that a lower value of
330 D_{n50} would result in a less turbulent flow inside the porous media and thus less wave energy
331 dissipated (??).

332 5. Discussion regarding the experimental design technique

333 The project design of a coastal structure should address the verification in laboratory of the
334 hydraulic performance and the failure modes that can affect the structure during its service life.
335 These predictions are influenced by many uncertainties, generally known as intrinsic and epistemic
336 uncertainty (?). Epistemic uncertainty is related to current knowledge regarding processes, models,
337 observations and methods. Intrinsic uncertainty (or statistical uncertainty) is aleatory and is
338 derived from outcomes that cannot be predicted and are treated as scholastic. This section discusses
339 the epistemic uncertainty associated to the experimental design technique and observations that
340 could have conditioned the results presented in Section 4.

341 Laboratory experiments for mound breakwaters in a wave flume should be based on the fol-
342 lowing model-prototype similarities: (1) dynamic similarity of wave progression and energy trans-
343 formation on the slope; and (2) flow similarity by satisfying fully turbulent regimes in the water
344 column and inside the porous structure. In terms of laboratory scale, Froude and Reynolds num-
345 bers cannot be kept simultaneously similar to their prototype values, so Froude scaling is used and
346 Reynolds number is assumed to be high enough to consider a fully turbulent flow. This assumption
347 is generally correct for the main armour layer, but it does not stand for filter layers and porous
348 core. If the flow regime inside the porous media (core and filter) in the model differs from that
349 inside the prototype, the hydraulic performance of the structure will be modified, known as the
350 scale effect (??).

351 In this study the dynamic similarity is satisfied using the sample space, $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ to
352 design the wave conditions in laboratory (see Fig. 2 and Appendix A). The sample space is based on
353 the interplay that the relative water depth, h/L , and the wave steepness, H/L , has on the hydraulic
354 performance of the structure. The selected wave conditions H and T (target) in the sample space
355 also depends on (i) the composition/geometry of the breakwater, (ii) the experimental conditions
356 (e.g. non-overtopping and/or non-breaking depth-limited conditions), and (iii) the characteristic
357 of the wave flume and its generation system. Figs. 3, 5-a.1, 5-b.1, 6a, 7a, 8a show the sample
358 spaces with colours according to the dimensionless variable analysed. By comparing each sample
359 space coloured by the dimensionless variable, it is possible to analyze the interplay that the relative
360 water depth, h/L , and the incident wave steepness, H_I/L , has on each point tested and its role
361 in the wave energy transformation and the breaker type on the structure. Moreover, the sample

362 space identifies the wave conditions tested in laboratory that adequately represent the hydraulic
363 performance of the maritime structure in prototype.

364 For a homogeneous and permeable breakwater, laboratory tests are more difficult to design
365 and to interpret because of the role played by the porous media in achieving the flow similarity
366 between model and prototype. In this regard, the experimental results presented in Section 4 has
367 a singularity highlighted in Figs. 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8. This singularity is characterized by low values of
368 H_I/L , all ranges of h/L , $B^*/L < 1$, and laminar/transition flow regimes inside the porous media
369 ($R_{e,p} < 300$). If the experimental tests of this singularity are scaled to prototype, e.g. with a 1:30
370 scale, the grain Reynolds number for all the experimental tests has a value of $R_{ep,prototype} > 2.5 \cdot 10^3$,
371 which represents a turbulent regime in prototype. Therefore, the origin of the observed singularity
372 in Section 4 is due to the difference in the flow regime between model and prototype (scale effect),
373 which implies that the flow similarity is not fulfilled even though the dynamic similarity is fulfilled.
374 As shown in Figures of Section 4, this scale effect changes the hydraulic performance of the structure
375 with maximum values of K_T^2 , maximum and minimum values of K_R^2 and observed breaker types
376 mainly surging and few weak bore according to increasing values of χ . The experimental tests that
377 suffer from scale effect do not represent the hydraulic performance of the prototype breakwater and
378 should not be used as results to develop design formulas. By the contrary, when the flow similarity
379 is fulfilled, wave energy transformation (reflection, transmission and dissipation) and wave breaker
380 types are ordered and identified according to values of χ , as it is observed in Figures of Section
381 4 and also pointed out in ?. The results in turbulent regime represent the performance of the
382 breakwater in prototype.

383 6. Conclusions

384 This study applied the methodology proposed by ? to estimate and analyze the wave energy
385 transformation on homogeneous and permeable mound breakwaters. The methodology is based
386 on a dimensional analysis that includes the main variables of wave train, porous media and slope
387 geometry that influence the hydraulic performance of mound breakwaters. For that, physical
388 experimentation was performed in a 2D wave flume for a conventional homogeneous and permeable
389 mound breakwater with two characteristic base widths, B^* , two seaward slope angles, α , and a
390 constant core diameter, $D_{n50,p}$. Wave conditions in laboratory were selected following a new
391 experimental technique based on the interplay that the relative water depth and the wave steepness
392 has on the hydraulic performance of the structure, and it is called the sample space [$\log(h/L)$
393 vertical-axis, $\log(H/L)$ horizontal-axis] (?). The following conclusions can derived from this study:

- 394 1. The analysis of the influence that each variable of the dimensional analysis has on wave energy
395 transformation shows that there is a relationship between the reflected K_R^2 , transmitted K_T^2
396 and dissipated D^* energy, and the product of the relative water depth, h/L , and the incident

397 wave steepness at the toe of the slope, H_I/L . This result reinforces the findings of ?, which
 398 states that the dynamic similarity parameter, $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$, identifies the regions of
 399 wave energy transformation and the wave breaker types.

- 400 2. A comparison of the permeable and homogeneous results obtained in laboratory to those
 401 of the impermeable breakwater tested numerically with the same slope angle highlighted
 402 significant changes in the performance of the permeable breakwater. The reflected energy
 403 decreased throughout the laboratory tests, in other words, in all the wave energy transfor-
 404 mation and observed wave breaker types. The results of the permeable slope shifted towards
 405 lower values of χ , and the variation of K_R^2 , K_T^2 , D^* and wave breaker types depend on both
 406 χ and the porous media represented by B^*/L , $D_{n50,p}/L$ and $R_{e,p}$.
- 407 3. The analysis of the incident wave train shows that the wave energy reflected mainly decreases
 408 (dissipation increases) as h/L increases and the wave energy transmitted mainly decreases
 409 as H_I/L increases.
- 410 4. The analysis of the porous media shows that for both tested breakwaters with different porous
 411 media area, the wave energy transformation and wave breaker types are grouped in the same
 412 intervals of χ for the same ranges of B^*/L . The wave energy reflected decreases as B^*/L
 413 increases and the transmitted energy takes maximum and minimum values with the lowest
 414 and highest range of B^*/L . The saturation regime in laboratory is achieved for $B^*/L > 1$.
- 415 5. The slope, α , is a dimensionless parameter that characterises the structure and orders the
 416 results. As the slope angle increases, the wave energy reflected increases too and dissipated
 417 energy decreases. The transmitted energy for both tested slope angles is practically the same.
- 418 6. The wave conditions selected for the three permeable and homogeneous breakwaters together
 419 with the characteristics of their porous media result in the occurrence of the three flow
 420 regimes inside the porous media, i.e: laminar regime ($R_{ep} < 150$), transition regime ($150 <$
 421 $R_{ep} < 300$) and turbulent regime ($R_{ep} > 300$). In the laminar and transition flow regimes
 422 the hydraulic performance of the structure with χ changes with respect to the hydraulic
 423 performance in the turbulent regime.
- 424 7. The experimental results shows that there is a singularity characterized by lower values of
 425 H_I/L , all ranges of h/L , $B^*/L < 1$, and with laminar and transition flow regimes inside
 426 the porous media ($R_{e,p} < 300$). In this singularity, the transmitted energy is maximum and
 427 the reflected energy takes maximum and minimum values with observed surging and weak
 428 bore breakers. The different hydraulic performance of the breakwater in the singularity is
 429 due to the scale effects produced in laboratory. The results in turbulent regime represent the
 430 performance of the breakwater in prototype.

431 The analysis of wave energy transformation and breaker types for each dimensionless variable
 432 collected in the dimensional analysis allows identifying the behaviour of each test performed in

laboratory. The application of the sample space $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ to get the functional relationship between h , H and T for designing wave conditions in laboratory (the new experimental technique) optimises the number of experiments and provides the information needed to (i) identify tests that meet the design criteria between model-prototype and wave generation requirements, and (ii) characterise the regions of wave energy transformation and breaker types for intervals of $\chi = (h/L)(H_I/L)$ and the breakwater performance with porous media and the slope angle. Hence, the methodology proposed by ? based on dimensional analysis and the derived new experimental technique, is a useful and simple method, which not only improves the analysis of wave energy transformation and breaker types on mound breakwaters, but also allows obtaining experimental results that characterize the hydraulic performance of the breakwater in prototype. The latter will help to develop future formulas and to improve the current ones by controlling the experimental technique and the methods in laboratory.

The application of the new experimental technique and the analysis of the results of this study are conducted from experimental tests that cover some ranges of the parameters that influence the hydraulic performance of the structure. However, this study has some limitations, such as, the analysis of some dimensionless variables, different breakwater typologies and the applicability of the new experimental technique on overtopping and/or damage studies. More experimental tests with wider range of variation, such as the slope angle α , or including other parameters, such as the relative core diameter $D_{p,50}/L$, should be tested as a future work. Moreover, this study was based on laboratory tests under non-overtopping, non-damage and non-breaking by depth-limited conditions, which would have changed the wave energy transformation in its interaction with the structure. It is therefore essential to extend and study the application of this experimental technique to other maritime studies and experimental requirements.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Professor Emeritus Miguel Á. Losada whose help, conceptualisation and earlier draft of the text made this study possible. The first author is funded through the Juan de la Cierva 2020 program (FJC2020-044778-I) by “Unión Europea – NextGenerationEU en el marco del Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia de España”, Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation.

Appendix A. Application of the new experimental technique

Appendix A describes the application of the sample space (Fig. 2) to obtain the wave conditions for the mound breakwaters tested in this study. The design methodology is explained for each slope angle tested in laboratory; that is: (A.1) the sample space for $\cot(\alpha) = 2$; (A.2) the sample space for $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$.

467 *A.1. Wave conditions for the physical models with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$*

468 From the experimental tests performed by ?, they concluded that the sample space, $[\log(h/L),$
469 $\log(H/L)]$, could be a suitable experimental design in laboratory, which: (i) optimizes the number
470 of experiments, (ii) verifies the design criteria between model-prototype, and (iii) quantifies the
471 regions of wave energy transformation and the wave breaker types. Then, the sample space elabo-
472 rated by ?, obtained from their tests, was used to design the sample spaces and to select the wave
473 conditions of the experimental tests of this work. Figure 9 shows the sample space for the physical
474 model tested in ?: (RMB) a permeable mound breakwater with a double-layer of cube armor, a
475 porous core (constant B^* and $D_{50,p}$), and a seaward slope angle $\cot(\alpha) = 2$. Based on the sample
476 space shown in Figure 9, the wave conditions for the physical model with $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ were selected
477 following the flow-chart of Fig. 2 with the following requirements:

- 478 • To ensure wave generation in Stokes I regime, the space $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ was reduced
479 (black solid lines) with respect to the space of the RMB - permeable mound breakwater with
480 main armor layer (blue dash lines):
 - 481 – Side A-B represents the limit between cnoidal and Stokes I regimes.
 - 482 – Side B-C represents the limit between Stokes II and Stokes I regimes.
- 483 • Wave conditions of point A and C mark the limit values of the dissipated region and the
484 reflected region, respectively, assumed for this mound breakwater type and geometry.
- 485 • Wave conditions of point B limit the wave height for non-overtopping conditions ($H < 0.14$
486 m) and Stokes I regime. This maximum wave height also ensures non-damage conditions.
- 487 • Wave conditions of point D mark the technical limitations of paddle generation: $H > 0.02$
488 m and $T > 1$ s.
- 489 • Wave conditions selected in the transition region (Fig. 9-b) to cover the wave breaker types:
490 strong plunging, strong bore and weak bore.

491 Table 4 includes in detail the wave conditions of Table 3 for the physical models HP-MB-1 and
492 HP-MB-3, both with slope angle $\cot(\alpha) = 2$. The pattern to increase or decrease T and H and the
493 tendency of the breaker types are indicated to follow each side of the sample space (black lines).
494 The number of tests were (3x38) for the model HP-MB-1 and (3x19) for the model HP-MB-3.

495 It should be noted that points A and C, which mark the region of maximum reflected wave
496 energy and maximum dissipated wave energy, respectively, are assumed values according to the
497 breakwater type and by known values from studies or real maritime works found in the literature.
498 It is recommended to verify these values with (1) energy calculation formulas (e.g. ??) or (2) some
499 more experimental tests to verify these limits.

Figure 9: Sample space $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ for the homogeneous and permeable mound breakwaters with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ (HP-MB-1 and HP-MB-3). (a) Black solid lines A-B-C-D, regular wave conditions chosen to cover reflected, dissipated and transition regions; (b) black solid arrows, regular wave conditions chosen in the transition region with breaker types strong plunging, strong bore and weak bore. Note that, colors of B^*/L range values and the breaker types are from the experimental results of the permeable mound breakwater with main armor (RMB) tested by ?.

500 *A.2. Wave conditions for the physical model with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$*

501 As mentioned in Section 2, the slope angle is considered as a plotting parameter of the results.
 502 The latter means that relationship between h/L and H/L is ordered by the slope angle of the
 503 breakwater. Therefore, regular wave conditions for the HP-MB-2 model with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$
 504 were programmed keeping constant the wave period, T , of the slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ and varying the
 505 wave height as,

Side	Wave conditions	$[(h/L)(H/L)]$	Pattern	Breaker types
A→B	$T = 3.0 \text{ s} - H = 0.0458 \text{ m}$ $T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.121 \text{ m}$	[0.0005 - 0.0022]	T decreases H increases	Surging → Strong bore
B→C	$T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.121 \text{ m}$ $T = 1.02 \text{ s} - H = 0.0313 \text{ m}$	[0.0022 - 0.0055]	T decreases H decreases	Strong bore → Weak plunging
C→D	$T = 1.02 \text{ s} - H = 0.0313 \text{ m}$ $T = 1.25 \text{ s} - H = 0.0205 \text{ m}$	[0.0019 - 0.0055]	T increases H decreases	Weak plunging → Strong plunging
D→A	$T = 1.25 \text{ s} - H = 0.0205 \text{ m}$ $T = 3.0 \text{ s} - H = 0.0458 \text{ m}$	[0.0005 - 0.0019]	T increases H increases	Strong plunging → Surging
A→C diagonal	$T = 3.0 \text{ s} - H = 0.0450 \text{ m}$ $T = 1.02 \text{ s} - H = 0.0313 \text{ m}$	[0.0005 - 0.0055]	T decreases H decreases	Surging → Weak plunging
Transition region	$T = 1.75 \text{ s} - H = 0.10 \text{ m}$ $T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.08 \text{ m}$	[0.0014 - 0.004]	T increases H decreases	Weak bore → Strong plunging

Table 4: Wave conditions tested for the homogeneous and permeable mound breakwaters with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$ (HP-MB-1 and HP-MB-3 models).

$$\left[\frac{h}{L} \right]_{1.5} = \left[\frac{h}{L} \right]_2$$

$$\frac{H_{1.5}}{L} = \frac{H_2}{L} \left(\frac{1/1.5}{1/2} \right)^2$$

506 Table 5 gathers conditions $[H, T]$ selected from the sample space showed in Figure 10. More
507 wave conditions in the transition region were also selected to cover the breaker types strong plunging,
508 strong bore and weak bore.

Side	Wave conditions	$[(h/L)(H/L)]$	Pattern	Breaker types
A→B	$T = 3 \text{ s} - H = 0.081 \text{ m}$ $T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.121 \text{ m}$	[0.00066 - 0.0022]	T decreases H increases	Weak bore → Strong bore
B→C	$T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.121 \text{ m}$ $T = 1.02 \text{ s} - H = 0.0556 \text{ m}$	[0.0022 - 0.0097]	T decreases H decreases	Strong bore → Weak plunging
C→D	$T = 1.02 \text{ s} - H = 0.0556 \text{ m}$ $T = 1.25 \text{ s} - H = 0.0364 \text{ m}$	[0.0034 - 0.0097]	T increases H decreases	Weak plunging → Strong plunging
D→A	$T = 1.25 \text{ s} - H = 0.0364 \text{ m}$ $T = 3 \text{ s} - H = 0.081 \text{ m}$	[0.00066 - 0.0034]	T increases H increases	Strong plunging → Strong bore
Transition region	$T = 2.14 \text{ s} - H = 0.12 \text{ m}$ $T = 2.5 \text{ s} - H = 0.08 \text{ m}$	[0.0014 - 0.003]	T increases H decreases	Strong bore → Strong plunging

Table 5: Regular wave conditions tested for the homogeneous permeable mound breakwater with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$ (HP-MB-2). (**) wave conditions imposing the same sample space of the slope $\cot(\alpha) = 2$.

509 Appendix B. Numerical tests using the IH-2VOF model

510 Model description

511 The IH-2VOF numerical model (?) was used in ? to model the interaction between waves and
512 an impermeable slope breakwater under non-overtopping conditions. IH-2VOF solves the two-
513 dimensional Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations outside the porous media using
514 the $k - \epsilon$ turbulent model to calculate the kinetic energy (k) and the turbulent dissipation rate
515 (ϵ). The free-surface is tracked by the Volume of Fluid (VOF) method (?). The flow through
516 the porous media is solved by the Volume-Averaged Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (VARANS)
517 equations. The final form of these equations are (more details in ?):

$$\frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_i} \quad (3)$$

Figure 10: Sample space $[\log(h/L), \log(H/L)]$ for the homogeneous and permeable mound breakwaters with slope $\cot(\alpha) = 1.5$ (HP-MB-2). Black solid lines A-B-C-D, wave conditions chosen to cover reflected, dissipated and transition regions. Black solid arrows, wave conditions chosen in the transition region with breaker types strong plunging, strong bore and weak bore.

$$\frac{1 + c_A}{n_p} + \frac{\overline{u_j}}{n_p^2} \frac{\partial \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{1}{\rho_w} \frac{\partial \overline{p}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\nu}{n_p} \frac{\partial^2 \overline{u_i}}{\partial x_i \partial x_j} - I - \overline{F_{gi}} \quad (4)$$

518 where t denotes time; u is the Reynolds-averaged velocity; p is the pressure; n_p is the core
519 porosity; ν is the kinematic viscosity; and $i, j = 1, 2$ where 1 and 2 denote the horizontal and vertical
520 directions, respectively. The \overline{X} represents the time-averaged volume-averaged of the variable X .
521 F_{gi} represents the body forces, namely gravity; and I is the hydraulic gradient, which represents
522 the flow resistance forces inside the porous media by the extended Forchheimer equation. The mass
523 added term appears on the left side of the equation, which affects the acceleration term, where
524 $c_A = \gamma_p(1 - n_p)/n_p$ is the added mass coefficient. The value of $\gamma_p = 0.34$ is generally considered
525 to be constant (?).

526 Since the breakwater tested with the numerical model was impermeable, parameters related
527 with the porous media and the flow resistance forces inside the porous media were not taken into
528 account ($n_p = 0$). The reader can find in ?'thesis an example of calibration of the coefficients
529 involved in the flow inside and outside the porous media for five breakwater typologies.

530 Numerical setup

531 A 2D domain of the wave flume described in Fig. 1 was reproduced in the IH-2VOF model. The
532 numerical domain was slightly shorter in the x-direction (15.6 m long) than the wave flume as the
533 dissipation ramp was substituted by an active absorption condition to reduce the number of cells.
534 A uniform mesh on the y-direction was used with a grid cell size of 0.5 cm. The x-direction was
535 divided in 2 subzones as defined in Fig. 11: (1) the 10.4 m-long outer region corresponding to the
536 wave generation zone with a cell size of 2 cm, (2) the region corresponding to the breakwater (wave-
537 structure interaction), where higher accuracy is needed, with a cell size of 1 cm. The total number

538 of cells in the numerical domain was 1017 (x-direction) x 201 (y-direction). A mesh sensitivity
539 analysis was performed to assess the computational cost and the accuracy of the results. Fig. 12
540 shows the free surface, η , of wave gauge positioned 2 m from the paddle (GA in Fig. 11), for a
541 numerical test characterized by regular wave conditions in paddle: (target) $H = 0.1059$ m and T
542 $= 2.5$ s. It is observed that with the mesh size described, the wave measured by GA has the same
543 wave period $T = 2.5$ s and practically the same wave height $H = 0.107$ m as the wave conditions
544 imposed to the paddle.

Figure 11: Numerical domain in IH-2VOF model: (a) mesh grid, (b) wave gauges position.

545 The numerical model was an impermeable slope, $\cot(\alpha) = 2$, over a impermeable caisson. The
546 wave interaction took place only over the impermeable slope. The active wave absorption condition
547 was considered at the generation boundary and at the end of the domain to reproduce the same
548 conditions as in the laboratory. Numerical wave gauges GA and GB measured the free surface
549 away from the structure and were positioned to study the mesh sensitivity. The reflected wave
550 energy, (K_R^2) were obtained by applying power spectral analysis with the data measured by gauges
551 G1, G2 and G3. The transmission coefficient (K_T^2) was computed with the data measured with
552 gauge G5, and for the impermeable and non-overtoppable slope $K_T^5 = 0$. Gauge G4, located at
553 the toe of the structure ($x = 0$), provided the total wave height at the toe of the breakwater (due
554 to the interaction of the incident and reflected wave trains). The time step was $\Delta_t = 0.05$ s.

555 Regular waves were simulated by setting $T = [1, 3]$ and varying H to cover the Iribarren domain,
556 $I_r = [2.3, 3.0, 3.5, 4, 4.8, 5]$, with a constant water depth $h = 0.4$ m (the same as in the physical
557 tests). The minimum number of Iribarren tested was limited by the maximum wave height in
558 non-overtopping conditions. Each test was simulated three time with 100 waves.

559 References

Figure 12: Free surface, η , measured at 2 m from paddle generation (wave gauge GA) with target wave conditions: $H = 0.1059$ m and $T = 2.5$ s.